
BIOPHYSICAL DESCRIPTORS OF NANOPARTICLE PROTEIN CORONAS

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✉ Vigneshwari Karunakaran Annapoorani^{1,2}, ✉ Sutapa Dutta^{1,3}, Oluwaseun Ajia¹, ✉ Ovidiu A. Petrisor^{1,2},
✉ Vladimir Lobaskin^{1,2}, and ✉ Nicolae-Viorel Buchete^{*1,2}

¹School of Physics, University College Dublin, Belfield, Dublin, D04 V1W8, Ireland

²Institute for Discovery, University College Dublin, Belfield, Dublin, D04 V1W8, Ireland

³Department of Physics, Tilka Manjhi Bhagalpur University, Ravindra Bhavan Rd, Sitanabad, Tatarpur, Bhagalpur, Bihar 812007, India

ABSTRACT

In biological environments, the formation of nano-bio molecular interfaces is a common result of the complex, dynamic interactions that occur at the surface of a nanoparticle (NP) or, more generally, at the surface of an engineered nanomaterial. These interactions involve a variety of biomolecules, mainly proteins, forming a nanoparticle-protein corona (NP-PC) molecular structure. Studies of the NP-PC's biophysical properties form a growing area of research. However, understanding, characterizing, and modelling systematically the biophysical properties and molecular interactions related to NP-PCs in biological environments remains a challenge. Understanding these processes should be achieved at a detailed atomic level; however, molecular studies of NP-PC models are difficult. Here, we report results of atomistic molecular dynamics (MD) conformational studies of several proteins known to participate in the corona composition of NPs entering the human body. Using several MD-refined protein structures in conjunction with molecular docking, we generate and analyze models of homo- and hetero-oligomers occurring within NP-PCs, their surface biophysical properties (e.g., the hydrophobic fraction of the solvent-accessible surface area, $SASA_H$), and their surface charge distributions. We use atomistic models of small TiO_2 and SiO_2 particles. Our approach unveils: (i) scaling relationships between the NP-PC protein composition and the resulting $SASA_H$ values, and (ii) a systematic way to characterize the transition from the “hard” (i.e., NP-proximal) to the “soft” (i.e., NP-distal) corona regions. This method of generating atomistic NP-PC models enables the efficient calculation of biophysical descriptors and, thus, could guide future studies of NP-PC biomolecular interactions and their effects (e.g., risk assessment of nano-toxicity) in diverse biological systems.

*corresponding author - buchete@ucd.ie

The development of a broad range of novel engineered nanomaterials (ENMs), such as nanoparticles (NPs),^{1,2} has facilitated significant progress in a variety of industrial applications, from nanomedicine³ to food science,⁴ household chemistry, cosmetics, or bio-compatible electronics.⁵ Because of their small size (diameter < 100 nm), ENMs have often unusual properties that could be useful.³ ENMs used in the biomedical or industrial applications cause health concerns due to increasing human exposure to NPs. For example, on average, it is estimated that Americans consume $10^{12} - 10^{14}$ NPs per day, titanium dioxide (TiO_2) NPs being one of the most common nanomaterials used as a primary agent for whitening, and as an anti-caking food additive.⁴ While the traditional risk assessment paradigm holds for all nanomaterials, many test guidelines and regulatory documents for the assessment of physicochemical properties, fate, exposure, and effects used for conventional chemicals need to be modified when applied to nanomaterials. The key to understanding the risks lies in the bio-nano interactions, namely in the understanding of how NPs can induce or trigger the biological pathways leading to adverse outcomes for human health and what physicochemical properties of the NP are responsible.⁶

A key factor that modulates bio-nano interactions inside cells and tissues is adsorption of biomolecules, primarily proteins, on the NP surface, and the associated formation of a nanoparticle-protein corona⁷ (NP-PC) molecular structure.^{1,2,7}

Recent studies indicate that the formation of NP-PC structures around NPs located in biofluids can modify the physicochemical characteristics of both natural and manufactured NPs.⁸ Nano-oncology and nanotoxicology are just a couple of several recent emerging applications involving NP-PCs. When compared to conventional chemotherapy and radiation therapy, the targeted administration of medications using NPs has demonstrated promising therapeutic potential to increase the effectiveness of cancer treatment.⁹ Ideally, current modeling approaches should allow researchers to understand and control both the thermodynamic and kinetic aspects of NP-PC formation, in order to allow NPs to function effectively in biological systems. Furthermore, conformational changes in the native structure of the component proteins may arise upon their interaction with NPs, modulating their functionality.¹⁰

Unfortunately, the lack of standards for information reported in scientific publications, variations in NP manufacture, heterogeneity in experimental and model systems, and the rapid pace of innovation in this field have made consistent systematic studies of NP–NP–biological interactions impractical.¹¹ Interestingly, the shape of the nanomaterial could also play an important role, with NP-PCs formed on nanorods exhibiting a distinct composition, with rankings of the relative abundance of different protein types as follows: acute phase proteins (APRs) being some of the most abundant, followed by other types, albumins, coagulation proteins, lipoproteins, complements, and immunoglobulins.¹²

It was also shown that formation of NP-PCs leads to an increase in the hydrophobicity of the microenvironment around Tyr residues of fibrinogen/transferrin.¹³ In a study of porous crystalline metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), UiO-66 MOFs adsorbed a greater amount of HSA proteins, induced large conformational rearrangement in HSA structures, and finally led to a significant reduction in the protein surface hydrophobicity, highlighting the importance of hydrophobicity as a biophysical modulator of NP-PC interactions.¹⁴

However, measuring, modeling and understanding the biophysical characteristics based on the molecular-level interactions that characterize the NP-PC formation and composition remains a key challenge in modern nanoscience, and studies of its biophysical features have recently emerged as a fast-growing field of research. Concretely, the hydrophobic and hydrophilic properties of the NP-PC surface can lead to biological and nanotoxicity-related effects that are difficult to characterize and predict quantitatively either experimentally or computationally. For example, proteins with sizes similar to the NPs (and, more generally, the ENMs) with which they interact can be absorbed more readily – another noteworthy characteristic.¹⁵

On a mesoscopic scale, it was also shown that changes in biophysics and frequently in biochemistry are the main drivers of protein–nanoparticle interactions.^{16,17} Both the nature of the NP and the properties of its surroundings have a significant impact on the corona’s composition and its creation.¹⁸ However, only comprehensive atomistic modelling studies will be able to fully address these changes. Currently, such molecular modeling studies are lacking.¹⁹

Here, we report a systematic molecular modeling study of building and characterizing biophysical properties on a broad range of NP-PCs, using as proof-of-concept five important proteins that are known to participate in the protein corona around NPs in the human body: Human Serum Albumin (HSA), Apolipoprotein (APO), Human Surfactant Protein D (HSP, chain D), Alpha-1 antitrypsin (AAT), and the Mucin 2 D3 domain (MUC).^{20–22} We also use as examples atomistic models of TiO_2 nanospheres and SiO_2 ²³ to generate and study the NP-PC interface around TiO_2 and SiO_2 nanoparticles and show how biophysical descriptor values can be estimated for atomistic models of NP-PCs.

As biophysical descriptors, we calculate the hydrophobic fraction of the solvent accessible surface area ($SASA_H$) and the corresponding fractions of charged SASA, denoted here as $SASA_+$ and $SASA_-$, to capture the effect of PC surface charges.^{24,25} $SASA_H$ values are particularly important as hydrophobicity is a crucial property that directly influences the stability of ENMs in general (and nanoparticles, in particular) and their ability to distribute throughout the body.^{3,5,26}

The efficient yet accurate characterization of NP-PC biophysical properties should be useful in future studies of NP–NP and NP–biomolecular interactions and their pos-

sible effects (e.g., nanotoxicity) in other, more specific biological systems.^{7,16,27}

In this paper, we present a multiscale framework using both atomistic/CG simulations to model and probe the detailed physicochemical properties of many proteins interacting with nanoparticles (Figure 1).¹⁹ We propose this multiscale framework starting from MD-based refinement and protein docking steps that allow us to model heterogeneous protein aggregates and thus NP corona structures. Here, we generate corona models for five common proteins and different relatively small inorganic NPs of different sizes. This general approach can be used with different types of NPs and proteins. We extract and discuss key biophysical descriptors of NP-PC structures, such as $SASA_H$, $SASA_+$, $SASA_-$ that may be critical for the NP fate and biological activity in living systems. Our approach allows us to unveil a systematic way to differentiate between two regimes of protein packing in NP-PC structures, the “hard” and “soft” corona regions.²⁸

As a first step of the multiscale framework proposed (Fig. 1), we use molecular dynamics (MD)^{29,30} to refine the experimental structures of the proteins modeled (e.g., HSA, AAT, HSP, APO, and MUC as used here). Subsequently, we used molecular docking to model the adsorption of relevant protein structures with the engineered nanomaterial relevant to the system of interest (e.g., here we used inorganic nanoparticles of SiO_2 , TiO_2 – nanosphere-shaped by using docking programs to combine ENM with proteins).¹ Once the many statistical models of the ENM-protein structure are generated, we analyze their composition and surface properties, describing the hydrophobic and electrostatic properties – key information to assessing the potential nanotoxicology of NPs.

To implement the computational framework illustrated in Figure 1 and the steps described above, we have run scripts that correspond to the pseudocode attached as Supplementary Information.

Molecular docking is generally used to predict the binding of only two molecular structures to form a complex. They are usually referred to as receptor and ligand, the goal of traditional molecular docking being to predict the non-covalent binding conformations and affinities.³¹ From a first-principles thermodynamic approach, the chemical potential can be used to determine the free energy of binding between the two molecular structures; however, this is computationally expensive. Instead docking tools rely on bespoke scoring functions to predict and rank docked conformations.³² Different docking tools use various approaches in calculating the molecular interactions, atomic energies, electrostatic and shape complementarity and ranking the conformational states of the molecular receptor-ligand complexes.³³

To derive the atomistic models of the NP-PC, we docked the representative structures of the proteins to the nanoparticles using PatchDock. PatchDock is a molecular docking algorithm that uses the complementarity of two molecules

in predicting the non-covalent binding conformations and ranking the binding affinities of these two molecules.³⁴ PatchDock employs a rigid protein docking algorithm by dividing the surfaces of the molecules into patches and quantifying their shape complementarity. The output of PatchDock includes measures such as the atomic contact energies (ACE), which is a component of the actual solvation-free energy of the molecular complex. ACE takes into account the electrostatic interactions and the entropic part of the solvation-free energy term.³⁵

While our approach can be extended to using other newer docking programs that may provide higher accuracy, PatchDock presents the major advantages of combining computational efficiency with versatility. Here, we use PatchDock as it supports multi-protein docking (i.e., up to 20 proteins in our case) and it can also model inorganic NPs of many types, shapes, and sizes. Key to our approach is the ability to generate many (i.e., often thousands for each case) atomistic NP-PC models by using multiple docking runs with multiple conformations using statistical sampling (see Figure S6). To overcome the docking limitation accuracy, we use multiple docking runs and perform a weighted analysis of the docking results using MD-refined conformations (see Fig. 2) of the subsequent docking results. An illustration of identifying and selecting atomistic protein conformations using MD refinement is shown in Figure 2 for the five proteins mentioned above (i.e., Human Surfactant Protein D (HSP, RCSB Protein Data Bank (PDB) code: 3DBZ, chain D),³⁶ Alpha-1 antitrypsin (AAT, 1QLP),³⁷ and Mucin 2 D3 domain (MUC, 6RBF),³⁸ Apolipoprotein (APO, 6V7M),³⁹ and Human Serum Albumin (HSA, 1E78)),⁴⁰ to generate diverse initial structures for subsequent docking with NPs or with partially formed NP-PC molecular structures.

A root mean square distance (RMSD) alignment-based analysis of atomistic trajectories generated during MD refinement for each protein is used to determine their representative, average equilibrium structures as well as their possible outlier conformations (i.e., most different from the representative ones).^{21,41} Finally, using these structures in conjunction with docking simulations,⁴² we generate both homo-oligomers and hetero-oligomers⁴³ and analyze their surface biophysical properties such as their hydrophobicity (i.e., the $SASA_H$ fraction) and surface charges ($SASA_+$ and $SASA_-$).⁴⁴

To investigate the conformational dynamics of our selected proteins in the NP-PC and to generate representative structures and outliers, MD simulations of each of the protein were performed in an NPT ensemble at a temperature of 310 K, and 1 atm pressure. We used the CHARMM36 force field with explicit TIP3P water molecules,⁴⁵ with a 2 fs integration step, a 12 Å cutoff for Lennard-Jones interactions, with each protein’s simulation run lasting a minimum of 300 ns, for a total of over 1.5 μ s overall simulation time. We note that, in this framework, very long MD simulations may not be necessary as the proteins used here are known to be structurally stable in physiolog-

Figure 1: Multiscale framework to combine atomistic representations of both proteins and NP. MD-refined protein conformations are combined with NP (or in general ENM) structures using docking and are analyzed further to determine biophysical descriptors (e.g., the composition and surface properties) of the NP-PCs generated. A main aim is to use atomistic models to calculate mesoscale descriptors that are relevant to biological interactions (e.g., $SASA_H$, $SASA_+$, $SASA_-$, protein-protein binding sites, etc.). This framework was implemented as detailed in the SI pseudocode.

ical conditions, adopting a narrow ensemble of compact structures. However, if the framework would be used for studying NP-PCs that include peptides or proteins with a broad equilibrium conformational ensemble, longer MD refinement trajectories and, possibly, their full Markov State Model-based MD analysis may become necessary.

The main aim of MD refinement is only to generate a relatively small but representative ensemble of compact conformation of each protein crystal structure that could be used in subsequent rigid protein docking to calculate a statistical range of NP-PC models for which mesoscopic biophysical descriptors (e.g., $SASA_H$) can be estimated. Here, we used the FreeSASA software to determine the solvent accessible surface area (SASA) of both protein structures and of protein clusters, including the NP-PC conformations.²⁴ Solvent accessible surface area (SASA) is an empirical measure of the degree to which a protein structure interacts with a surrounding solvent rather than with itself.⁴⁶ Two independent algorithms were used to compare the high precision results from the SASA calculations for verification.²⁴

According to the classical Lee and Richards²⁵ method used here, the solvent accessibility of the molecule can be derived by dividing its surface into equidistant points, and rolling a virtual sphere (a.k.a. “probe”) over the surface regions with a spherical probe of radius of 1.4 Å where the

probe represents the solvent and is being rolled over the van der Waals surface of the protein atoms.⁴⁷ The SASA value of a larger molecule or molecular complex is calculated as the surface area found by the center of the probe.²⁵ We note that analytical calculations of the surface area are also possible and may be useful in particular cases such as high molecular roughness.⁴⁸

Figure 2 shows the RMSD trajectory calculated for the average structure of the MD of HSP, HSA, AAT, APO, and MUC. Along the x-axis is the time duration of simulation in ns and along the y-axis is the RMSD. The average structure is marked with a black star, while the most prominent outliers are marked with a black square. The molecular structures in Figure 2 depict the most noticeable conformational differences between the respective average structures and the labelled outliers. The approach illustrated here for generating MD-refined structures for both representative (i.e., average-like) and outlier conformations is general, transferable and likely to work for most protein structures though it is computationally intensive as MD atomistic data is needed for at least hundreds of nanoseconds. However, we note that recent advances in generating representative protein conformations provided by tools such as AlphaFold2⁴⁹ and BioEmu⁵⁰ may also be used at this step in our framework in future implementations. Based on MD-refined conformations, in conjunction with docking, the range of

Figure 2: RMSD plot of typical MD trajectories of the corona proteins: HSA, APO, MUC, HSP, AAT (see text for details). Average structures (black stars), and the most prominent outliers are marked (black squares). Protein graphs highlight conformational differences between the corresponding average structures and the most prominent outliers.

Figure 3: Atomistic NP-PC models calculated for a small ($\Phi = 4$ nm), spherical SiO_2 NP (colored by atom type, Si shown in yellow), built by docking different proteins on the NP surface in sequential order. (A, B) Representations of the same NP corona model using 15 different proteins. (C, D) Representations of the same NP-PC extended to include 20 proteins. (A, C) NP-PC structures are colored by secondary structure (i.e., helices shown in purple & blue, and beta sheets – yellow). (B, D) NP-PC surface colored by residue type (i.e., red – acidic, blue – basic, green – polar/hydrophilic, grey – hydrophobic).

biophysical properties of possible NP coronas (e.g., surface charges, hydrophobicity, specific PPIs, etc.) are estimated. For various NP types and protein compositions, these models can be used to calculate NP-PC descriptors (e.g., $SASA$, $SASA_H$, $SASA_+$, $SASA_-$, etc.), in order to study how values of mesoscopic descriptors emerge from the individual properties of the NP and the corona proteins. The next step, docking of protein conformations to the NP surface to form models of NP-PC structures is shown in Figure 3 (see also additional NP-PC structures in Figs. S1 and S2) for models including 15 (Fig. 3, A, B) and 20 (Fig. 3, C, D) proteins, respectively. Comprehensive results for $SASA_H$ calculated including a systematically increasing number of proteins are shown in Fig. S3 (e.g.,

in Fig. S3(A), continuous lines represent the $SASA_H$ of homooligomers PCs, without nanoparticles, built using sequential docking (i.e., docking proteins one by one and selecting the results with the highest docking score, Fig. S6) and colored by protein type). The convergence of $SASA_H$ values to a narrow range (i.e., approximately 0.37 to 0.45) is noticeable, as they depend much less on the nanoparticle type as larger number of proteins (N) adsorb to the PC structures.

Similarly, the corresponding values for other key descriptors such as $SASA_+$ (the positive SASA fraction), and $SASA_-$ (the fraction of negatively charged SASA) are shown in Figure S4, illustrating the corresponding conver-

gence ranges as well (i.e., approximately 0.06 to 0.17). In this case, the final $SASA_+$ and $SASA_-$ values are dependent on both the NP type and the protein composition, even for large N values.

Interestingly, we note that if the $SASA_H$ values are analyzed separately for each protein type (i.e., using only one type of protein to build “holigomeric” NP-PCs, see results in Fig. S5), all cases present a similar trend with $SASA_H$ values, converging noticeably to a narrow range that is specific to each protein type. This is easy to understand, as adsorbing an increasing number of proteins to a NP-PC structure leads to $SASA_H$ values becoming less dependent on each specific NP type.

In Figure 4, we illustrate these saturation trends emerging from the $SASA_H$ data shown in Figs. S3 and S5. Here, the $SASA_H$ values are shown normalized with respect to the highest values calculated for various models of NP-PC, for each NP type and size (i.e., as shown in each panel) and for each protein type included. To capture this general dependency of NP-PC $SASA_H$ values quantitatively, we propose a simple saturation equation:

$$A_{total} = A_H e^{-m_H N} + A_S (1 - e^{-m_S N}) \quad (1)$$

that captures effectively two observed regimes (i.e., for small and, respectively, large number of proteins included in each corona model, N). Here, A_H , m_H , A_S , and m_S are the parameters that modulate the behavior in each regime. These two regimes (illustrated also in Figures S7 and S8 for clarity) are evident in the data: the first region corresponds to fewer proteins (termed previously, qualitatively, as the “hard corona”, HC),²⁸ and a second regime for large N -values that depends only on protein-level properties (“soft corona”, SC).²⁸ In the supplementary Table S1, we report the A_H , m_H , A_S , and m_S parameter values calculated for homo-oligomeric NP-PC structures generated for each type of protein and NP combinations used in this study.

Interestingly, this suggests that, for realistic NP-PC models (i.e., when there is sufficient time for equilibration and, thus, for a large number of proteins to be adsorbed on the NP surface) the $SASA_H$ values corresponding to the equilibrated corona structure will depend only on the properties of the protein oligomers, and be rather independent of the NP type.

Figure 5 illustrates quantitatively the two-regime properties of $SASA_H$ values calculated for NP-PC structural models. While we expect this dependency to be rather generic, as illustrated by data in Fig. 4 and Figs. S7 and S8, here we show results obtained for a set of homooligomeric MUC corona models built for a SiO_2 nanoparticle (with a diameter $\Phi = 5$ nm, corresponding to data in Fig. 4C).

The $SASA_H$ dependency on the corona size (i.e., numbers of proteins adsorbed) reported here was calculated for statistical atomistic models of NP-PC at equilibrium. In our framework, the properties of both the hard and soft corona regions are averaged over many statistical realizations and

thus aspects such as the more transient nature of the soft corona are not sampled directly.^{51–53}

A basic understanding of the physicochemical properties of NPs that impact the adsorption of proteins is key to the design and development of well-characterized ENMs, in general, and of NPs, in particular.^{3,5} Calculating and measuring well-defined physics-based descriptors can positively impact applications in diverse areas (e.g., such as biomolecular sensing, where ENMs can be employed for the detection of multiple biomolecules⁵⁴). For example, it was reported that essential proteins from blood adsorb strongly on the surfaces of the NPs, with both the number of binding sites and the corresponding binding constants depending heavily on NP type.⁵⁴ Similarly, surface hydrophobicity values were suggested as being a particularly important biophysical property that directly influences the stability of ENMs in general (and nanoparticles, in particular) and their ability to distribute in biological environments.^{3,5,26}

Here, we present a computational framework (see Fig. 1) that can be used to generate a broad range of models of atomistic structures of NP-PC systems (Fig. 3) based on a large set of statistically diverse molecular docking runs, performed either sequentially (e.g., Fig. S6) or in parallel (i.e., by docking dimers or even oligomers). In this framework, we generate many NP-PC structures by docking in various combinations proteins with various MD-refined conformations to generate both homo- and hetero-oligomeric coronas. These corona structures are finally analyzed to study and extract statistical values for descriptors of their corresponding biophysical properties. We note that advances in generating representative protein conformations provided by tools such as AlphaFold2⁴⁹ and BioEmu⁵⁰ may also be used at this step in our framework in the future for more computationally efficient implementations. Similarly, the accuracy of the molecular docking stage can be modulated by comparing results obtained for different docking programs.

As a proof of concept, we studied five important blood proteins (HSA, HSP, AAT, APO, MUC), and a variety of statistical models of protein coronas formed around relatively small nanoparticles of TiO_2 and SiO_2 to assess the range of possible statistical models that can be generated within the framework proposed here. To our knowledge, this is the first attempt to build protein corona models with atomistic-level resolution by using docking of MD-refined structures of several different protein and NP types. While further testing with alternative modeling and experimental methods is possible, we have achieved promising solutions for the statistical models of NP-PC structures.

The structural models of NP coronas allow us to calculate new biophysical descriptors, such as $SASA_H$, $SASA_+$, $SASA_-$, shape-based, etc., that are key to the fate and biological activity of the NPs in living organisms. Interestingly, our statistical estimates of biophysical descriptors provide a detailed atomistic description of both hard and soft protein shells of NP-PCs, as well as a detailed charac-

Figure 4: Normalized $SASA_H$ values calculated for NP-PC several models built using two types of spherical NPs (TiO_2 and SiO_2) of different size and using five different proteins (see text). The $SASA_H$ dependency on the number of proteins included (N) is shown in each panel for models of: (A, B, C) SiO_2 NPs ($\Phi = 2$ nm, $\Phi = 4$ nm, and $\Phi = 5$ nm), and (D) a TiO_2 NP ($\Phi = 4$ nm). Data for different proteins is illustrated using different markers as shown (see legends). Note that the data for the smallest NP (SiO_2 , $\Phi = 2$ nm, panel A) presents the largest fluctuations as the NP approaches the average size of the proteins used.

terization of their biomolecular properties such as surface residues, their type (e.g., fraction of charged SASA), degree of anisotropic coverage of the NP surface, the spatial (i.e., 3D) distribution of proteins in the corona, and other details on specific protein–NP and protein–protein interactions. We described a phenomenological equation for the key $SASA_H$ values of NP-PC structures that allows a quantitative characterization of the two main phases of corona regions (hard and soft coronas, see Figures 4 and 5, and parameters listed in Table ST1).

Using the NP-PC modeling framework presented here allows us to highlight several important, yet often ignored, observations related to NP-PC structures, such as the possibility of a non-uniform protein coverage of a NP’s surface, even in hard corona regions. The resulting rather heterogeneous and rough NP-PC surface topography may be important in modulating biological interactions and may present a non-trivial size dependence. To increase the accuracy of NP-PC models, better computational models of protein–protein interactions are needed, as they may play an even stronger role than specific NP–protein interactions. For example, NP-PC structures may play roles in specific biomolecular interactions, with clear implications to understanding nanotoxicity,⁵ to the design of new nanocarrier-based systems for drug delivery³ or, possibly, to control the sequestration of iron compounds by using

chelating agents or to promote or modulate aggregation of various amyloidogenic proteins.^{55,56}

Kinetic aspects of sequential protein adsorption of different proteins while forming NP-PC structures are also important and future frameworks may include them based on either experimental data, when available, or based on the results of dynamic simulations such as Kinetic Monte-Carlo, Brownian dynamics or coarse-grained modeling⁵⁷ and simulations⁵⁸ of protein adsorption and protein–protein interactions in the corona.^{5,19,22,59,60} Experimental studies have demonstrated that hard and soft corona structures are formed on silica NPs incubated with albumin and other proteins.^{61,62} While these data do not currently allow for a direct comparison with our computational model, we are planning to extend this work in our next study. Methods for accurately including the effect of coating NPs (e.g., with PEG) may also be important to incorporate in future studies.⁶³

Our approach will help advance the understanding of the formation of NP-PC structures and their biophysical properties that can be further extended in building more accurate NP-PC models and applications. This method is simple and computationally efficient and complementary to other experimental^{2,64} and modeling-based^{60,59} NP-corona analysis methods in this field. Analyzing the resulting

Figure 5: Dependence of normalized $SASA_H$ values for a set of homooligomeric MUC corona models built for a SiO_2 NP ($\Phi = 5$ nm, Fig. 4C). The two regimes are clearly evidenced with linear fits for the $\ln(SASA_H)$ shown in red for the “hard” corona (i.e., small number of proteins, N) and blue for the “soft” corona (i.e., large N) regimes, respectively.

atomistic, detailed NP-PC structures is one of the major (and, currently, not fully addressed) requirements for characterizing and even predicting the biophysical properties of a variety of experimentally relevant NP-PC biomolecular structures.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information.

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.5c02353>.

Additional examples of atomistic corona models constructed for nanoparticles of different types and sizes (Figures S1 and S2), $SASA_H$, $SASA_+$, $SASA_-$ values calculated for several nanoparticles as a function of the number of proteins included (Figures S3-S5 and Table S1), an illustration of the sequential docking approach to building a corona model (Figure S6), and illustrations of common dependency trends of the $SASA_H$ fraction on the size of NP-PC structures (Figures S7 and S8) (PDF) Pseudocode illustrating the framework for constructing NP-PC structural models for homo- and hetero-oligomers (PDF) Transparent Peer Review report available (PDF)

AUTHOR INFORMATION

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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